

Some aspects of applying asymptotic methods to the analysis of nonlinear dynamics of complex systems

Let us consider the application of asymptotic methods to the analysis of the dynamics of complex systems. To obtain a solution to the differential equation of the nonlinear dynamics of an oscillator, an asymptotic approach was essentially applied, associated with a small parameter for the nonlinear component of the equation. That is, it was assumed that the influence of the nonlinear component of the system under study is small.

Keeping only the first nonlinear component of the expansion of the function $\text{Sin}x$

$$|x| \ll 1, \quad \text{Sin}x \approx x - \frac{x^3}{6} \rightarrow \frac{d^2 \mathcal{G}}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2 \mathcal{G} = 0, \quad (1)$$

the equation of nonlinear oscillations is obtained in the form:

$$\frac{d^2 \mathcal{G}}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2 \mathcal{G} - \frac{\omega_0^2}{6} \mathcal{G}^3 = 0 \quad (2)$$

Considering the case of only “small” nonlinear oscillations of the system, equation (2) can be represented in the form

$$\frac{d^2 \mathcal{G}}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2 \mathcal{G} - \varepsilon \frac{1}{6} \omega_0^2 \mathcal{G}^3 = 0, \quad (3)$$

where the parameter $\varepsilon \ll 1$ is introduced artificially.

The solution of equation (3) was represented as the sum of two functions: the first component corresponded to the solution of a linear problem, and the second - to a nonlinear one, provided that the addition (perturbation) of the linear system is small and there is a "small" parameter ε in the component of the equation of motion

$$\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_0 \text{Sin} \omega t + \varepsilon \mathcal{G}_0 \text{Sin} 3 \omega t, \quad (4)$$

where $\varepsilon \ll 1$ is a dimensionless constant (disturbance parameter), and $\mathcal{G}_0 \ll 1$ is the amplitude of oscillations of the linearized harmonic oscillator.

It should be noted that as a "small" parameter, one can take the value $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{6}$, or assume that the ω_0 frequency of the linear oscillator is a "small" value.

Any physical theory formulated in its entirety is very complex from a mathematical point of view. Therefore, in the development of the theory and its further development, a special role is played by the simplest limiting cases that assume an analytical solution. It is thanks to the use of asymptotic methods that it is possible to significantly simplify the construction of the solution.

In addition, asymptotic approaches are closely related to the physical essence of the theory, allowing for better penetration into it. Quite often, these methods provide the possibility of a unified approach to different, at first glance, problems, allowing to reveal their hidden unity and commonality.

But the disadvantages of asymptotic methods are the locality of the obtained solutions (i.e., technical difficulties in obtaining approximate analytical solutions while maintaining the expansion of the desired function in high approximations (at least the highest two approximations)).

Therefore, in practice, as a rule, a maximum of two terms of the expansion of the desired function are used: as we indicated in the example of the dynamics of a rotating oscillator, the first component of the expansion is responsible for the linear problem of the system under study, and the second - for the influence of the nonlinear behavior of the phenomenon or process under study.

As for ordinary differential equations, partial differential equations and their systems with a "small" parameter, it is necessary to distinguish two classes of equations depending on the location of the "small" parameter:

- - a regular type equation, in which the parameter of the asymptotic expansion of the desired function is located inside the equation (as in our discussed example)

$$\frac{d^2 g}{dt^2} + fr(t) \frac{dg}{dt} + \varepsilon g(t)g^3 = F(t) \quad (5)$$

- - and singular type equations, when the "small" parameter is at the highest derivative (an important class of equations in the mechanics of a deformed solid, in particular in the theory of inhomogeneous rods, plates and shells,

quantum physics, aero-hydro-mechanics, heat-mass transfer and other branches of science and technology)

$$\varepsilon^2 \frac{d^2 \mathcal{G}}{dt^2} + fr(t) \frac{d\mathcal{G}}{dt} + \lambda g(t) \mathcal{G}^3 = F(t) \quad (6)$$

Наприклад, за умови великих частот лінеаризованої системи (6), досліджуваної у нашому прикладі, диференціальне рівняння задачі може бути представлено у виді:

For example, under the condition of high frequencies of the linearized system ($\omega_0^2 \gg 1$), studied in our example, the differential equation of the problem can be represented in the form:

$$\varepsilon^2 \frac{d^2 \mathcal{G}}{dt^2} + 6\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{G}^3 = 0, \quad (7)$$

where $\varepsilon^2 = \frac{6}{\omega_0^2}$, is the "small parameter" for the highest derivative.

For an approximate analytical solution of a nonlinear differential equation of regular type (3.3), the perturbation method is used, when the sought function is represented in the form of a series with respect to a "small" parameter ε :

$$\mathcal{G}(t) = \mathcal{G}_0(t) + \varepsilon \mathcal{G}_1(t) + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{G}_2(t) + \dots = \sum_{i=0}^n \varepsilon^i \mathcal{G}_i(t) \quad (8)$$

Considering only two terms of the expansion (8) and substituting the function $\mathcal{G}(t) = \mathcal{G}_0(t) + \varepsilon \mathcal{G}_1(t)$ into the differential equation of problem (7), we obtain:

$$\frac{d^2[\mathcal{G}_0(t) + \varepsilon \mathcal{G}_1(t)]}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2[\mathcal{G}_0 + \varepsilon \mathcal{G}_1^2] - \varepsilon \frac{\omega_0^2}{6} \mathcal{G}[\mathcal{G}_0 + \varepsilon \mathcal{G}_1^2]^3 = 0 \quad (9)$$

By equating the coefficients at the same powers of the parameter ε , we obtain a system of differential equations of the form:

$$\varepsilon^0: \quad \frac{d^2[\mathcal{G}_0(t)]}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2[\mathcal{G}_0(t)] = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$\varepsilon^1 \frac{d^2[\mathcal{G}_1(t)]}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2[\mathcal{G}_1(t)] - \varepsilon \frac{\omega_0^2}{6}[\mathcal{G}_0(t)^3] = 0, \quad (11)$$

The first equation (10) describes the solution of a linear problem (the desired function $\mathcal{G}_0(t)$ and its derivatives in the first degree), and the second differential equation (11) is a non-homogeneous $\mathcal{G}_1(t)$ differential equation with respect to the function

$$\frac{d^2[\mathcal{G}_1(t)]}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2[\mathcal{G}_1(t)] = \varepsilon \frac{\omega_0^2}{6}[\mathcal{G}_0(t)^3], \quad (12)$$

the right-hand side of which is the desired function $\mathcal{G}_0(t)$ from the solution of the previous linear equation (10).

Thus, using standard procedures for solving homogeneous and inhomogeneous ordinary differential equations (the desired function depends on one parameter t).

A feature of differential equations of the singular type (with a “small parameter” at the highest derivative) is the fact that in equations of the type (6, 7) even at very small values of the “small” parameter it is not possible to neglect the first component of the equation of the studied process due to obtaining in this case a trivial solution of the linear component of the desired function.

Recently, much attention has been paid to methods that allow expanding the scope of application of asymptotic approaches by the parameter of the expansion of the desired function, especially for systems with time-varying parameters, in particular mass, density, geometry, frequency of oscillations and others.

It should be noted that today there are already effective asymptotic methods for solving boundary value problems of the mechanics of a deformable solid, which are reduced to linear and geometrically nonlinear singular, i.e. special differential equations with variable coefficients, in particular in the presence of a small parameter at the highest derivative.

In particular, we are talking about the method of phase integrals (or the WKB method - proposed by French physicists Wentzel, Kramers and Brillouin, which was applied in particular to the solution of the Schrödinger equation of type (6) to the problems of quantum mechanics and subsequently found wide application in various fields of knowledge.

I cannot help but say for this audience that the employee of the Dnipro Polytechnic, Associate Professor Dolgov Oleksandr Mikhailovich, applied the specified method to the solution of the problem of the stability of conical shells of aircraft reinforced with frames under combined external loading.

It should be noted that the use of an asymptotic approach based on the existence of a physical, or artificial, "small" parameter requires determining the value of the parameter to which the obtained approximate asymptotic solution is suitable for practical application, which in turn is a problem that must be solved in each study separately. In the absence of analytical estimates of the parameter value are used based on a comparison of the approximate analytical approach with the direct numerical integration method, if such a possibility exists.

The hybrid VKB - Galerkin method (proposed 30 years ago by the author of this lecture) allows you to build an approximate solution to a fairly wide range of linear and nonlinear problems in mechanics and other branches of science and technology, in particular for systems with parameters that vary in coordinates and time, for which in the general sense there are no exact analytical methods for integrating the corresponding differential equations. A feature of the proposed hybrid method is the possibility of obtaining approximate analytical solutions for the specified systems, which are described by singular differential equations with variable coefficients and their systems regardless of the value of the parameter of the asymptotic expansion of the desired function of the problem.

It should be emphasized that even approximate analytical solutions are necessary as a basis for the effective application of direct numerical methods for the analysis of complex systems, such as finite and boundary element methods, which in many cases

allow solving such problems of mechanics as the stress-strain state of a real structure, its stability and dynamic behavior.

It should be noted that in some cases it is simply not possible to obtain solutions to some problems based on direct numerical methods of integrating differential equations.

For example, a differential equation with a so-called "turning point" does not allow obtaining a reliable numerical result over the entire interval of change of the desired function.